

A Study on Entrepreneurial Satisfaction towards M-Banking Services in Hosur Taluk

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Abstract

Banking is the backbone of every industry and technology plays an important role in every industry. The liberalization and globalization of our economy took place almost a decade ago. The phrases such as "the customer is the king in our business," is no more myth but have turned out to be a reality. In other words, we need as much control over our finances as possible and at all time-remote control. This is possible using mobile banking. So we can say it as a 24 hours service. In this method, the user can able to do all their works without going to the bank. The topic that was hence chosen for this research is "A Study on Entrepreneurial Satisfaction towards M-banking services in Hosur taluk". A sample size of 90 account holders with different banks was taken for the study and random sampling method was used. Both primary & secondary data were used for the study. This research is based on the data collected through "Questionnaire" with Mobile banking user.

Keywords: M-banking, Financial Services, Online Banking

Introduction

Mobile banking is a service provided by a bank or other financial institution that allows its customers to conduct some financial transactions remotely using a mobile device such as a mobile phone or tablet. Mobile banking differs from mobile payments, which involves the use of a mobile device to pay for goods or services at the point of sale or remotely, analogously to the use of a debit or credit card to effect an EFTPOS payment.

The traditional brick and mortar are done from fixed branch premises, where the customer has to go personally for carrying out business transactions. Through mobile banking, the customer can conduct a host of banking transactions and inquiries through the mobile. Mobile banking can also be carried through a mobile van with or without computerized banking system. The mobile van moves from place to place on designated routes at designated hours and the customers can transact their banking business, such as deposit, withdrawal, cheque collection, draft issuance, pass book updates, etc. Mobile banking helps the customer to do his account

management, electronically which was earlier possible through internet banking. Mobile banking service is divided into two categories:

SMS Based: This service can be availed from any mobile having SMS based service. The customer types the required keywords and PIN number and sends the message to the predefined number.

Menu Based: The customer downloads and installs the application on the mobile. Whenever the customer wants any sort of information, he selects the application, selects the request from the menu and sends the request to the designated number. This request internally sent as SMS text. The central computer at the bank sends back the result to him.

Functionalities of Mobile Banking

Mobile banking functionalities have been divided into three parts. In the public category, the customer can openly access the exchange rates and interest rates of the economy as well as the banks. In the private category, the customer can check the account balances, can administer the credit lines and can check the transactions. While conducting the transactions, mobile banking helps in transfer of funds, and in paying invoices.

Figure Flow Chart for Functions of Mobile Banking

Mobile Banking in India

Mobile banking has not widely accepted, but there is significant growth found in recent years after the spread of the mobile network. Since 1995 in India, there is found tremendous growth in mobile users in India. In the past two years, mobile banking users have increased three times if we compare the use of either debit card or credit card. Now, 32 banks had been granted permission to operate Mobile Banking in India till June 30, 2009, of which 6, belonged to the State Bank Group, 12 to nationalized banks and 13 to private/foreign banks. The RBI has adopted Bank Led Model in which mobile phone banking is promoted through business correspondents of banks. Recently, Indian banks are offering followings facilities through mobile banking: 1) Check account balance 2) Get automatic updates on bill payments 3) Get automatic updates scheduled payments 4) Mini account statement 5) SMS alert about deposit and withdrawal 6) Electronic fund transfer 7) Bill Payment, Donations, Subscriptions etc. 8) Information about new schemes, changes in charges and interest rates 9) Stop payment order and cheque book request 10) ATM and branch locating 11) Mobile Top Up, Recharge of Other DTHs, 12) Merchant payment, SBI life insurance premium 13) De-mat Enquiry Service 14) Real-time stock quotes.

History: The earliest mobile banking services used SMS, a service known as SMS banking. With the introduction of smart phones with WAP support enabling the use of the mobile web in 1999, the first European banks started to offer mobile banking on this platform to their customers. Mobile banking has until recently (2010) most often been performed via SMS or the mobile web. Apple's initial success with iPhone and the rapid growth of phones based on Google's Android (operating system) have led to increasing use of special client programs, called apps, downloaded to the mobile device. With that said advancements in web technologies such as HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript have seen more banks launching mobile web-based services to complement native applications.

Advantages of Mobile Banking

Time-Saving: Instead of allocating time to walk into a bank, you can check account balances, schedule and receive payments, transfer money and organize your accounts when you're on the go.

Convenient: The ability to access bank accounts, make payments, and even track investments regardless of where you are can be a big advantage. Do your banking at a time and place that suits you, instead of waiting in queues.

Secure: Generally, good mobile banking apps have a security guarantee or send you an SMS verification code you need to input to authorize a payment for added security. Mobile banking is said to be even more secure than online/internet banking.

Easy Access to Your Finances: with the introduction of mobile banking, you can access your financial information even beyond the working hours. It helps to avail banking services even by making a call to the bank.

Disadvantages of Mobile Banking

- Mobile banking users are at risk of receiving fake SMS messages and scams.
- The loss of a person's mobile device often means that criminals can gain access to your mobile banking PIN and other sensitive information.
- Modern mobile devices like Smartphone and tablets are better suited for mobile banking than old models of mobile phones and devices.
- Regular users of mobile banking over time can accumulate significant charges from their banks.
- Even though there are 1.5 billion computers on the Internet and 4.5 billion people using mobile phones, there's currently no significant operating system supporting the mobile space. "Hackers want to do the least amount of work for the biggest gain.
- Most mobile banking apps need an internet connection to be able to operate, so if you live in a rural area or experience problems with your internet connection, then you won't be able to access your account. The same applies if your mobile phone runs out of battery.

Review of Literature

RenjuChandran (2014) founded that new technology has rapidly altered the traditional ways of doing banking business. An entrepreneur can view the accounts, get account statements, transfer funds, purchase drafts by just making a few key punches. Availability of ATMs and plastic cards, EFT, electronic clearing services, internet banking, mobile banking, and phone banking; to a large extent avoid customers going to branch premises and has provided a wider range of services to the customers. Mobile banking is a system that allows customers of a financial institution to conduct some financial transactions through a mobile device such as a mobile phone or personal digital assistant. Banking apps can make bill paying and bank account management incredibly convenient,

but the risk of identity theft is a major downside. Fortunately, it's easy to avoid most of the pitfalls with commonsense solutions like strong password protection and secure connections. By keeping these security tips in mind, you can enjoy a safer mobile banking experience.

Manav Aggarwal (2014) discussed that Banking is the backbone of every industry and technology plays an important role in every industry. The role of technology is increasing very rapidly day by day, which is also promoting the banking industry. Banking is one of the largest financial institutions which regularly explore the opportunity of technology to provide better customer services. In today's business, technology has been the largest indicators of growth and competitiveness. The banking industry today is in the era of its revolution. The increased dominance of mobile phones provides exciting opportunities for the growth of mobile banking. Mobile banking is a system that helps the customers to conduct some financial transactions with the help of their mobile devices. Mobile banking is a revolution that is driven by the world's one of the fastest growing sector, mobile communication technology.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the basic concept of Mobile Banking in India.
- To know the satisfaction level of M-Banking among the Entrepreneur.

Limitation of the Study

1. The study is conducted only in Hosur taluk
2. The study is restricted to the limited number of respondents.i.e. 120 due to time constraint

Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected through questionnaire from account holders with different banks in Hosur Taluk. The secondary sources have been collected from journals and websites.

Sampling Design

Convenient sampling technique was adopted by 120 account holders with different banks in Hosur Taluk.

Tools for Analysis

For processing and interpretation of data, the researcher has applied the statistical tools such as; Percentage analysis and Likert scale method is used to analyze the data.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Gender wise Classification of M-Banking users

S.No	Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	83	69%
2	Female	37	31%
	Total	120	100%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 1, Among the total respondent, 69% of respondents are male and the remaining 31% are female.

Table 2 Age-wise Classification of M-Banking Customers

S.No	Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 40	45	38%
2	40-60	60	50%
3	Above 60	15	12%
	Total	120	100%

Source: Primary Data

From the data collected, it is revealed that 38% of respondents are under the age group of below 40 years, 50% of respondents are in the age group of 40 to 60 years, and only 12% of the respondents belong to the age group of Above 60 years.

Table 3 Customer Satisfaction Level

S.No	Factors	Opinion					Total
		HS	S	N	DS	HDS	
1	Fund Transfer	60	25	12	14	9	120
2	IMPS-Immediate payment services	40	25	22	16	17	120
3	Inquiry services	45	32	25	9	9	120
4	Bill payment(Unit bill, Cash bill)	48	27	15	10	25	120
5	Security /Safety System	35	20	25	20	20	120
6	Time Savings	45	25	25	15	10	120

S.No	Factors	Opinion					Total	Mean Score	Rank
		HS	S	N	DS	HDS			
1	Fund Transfer	60	25	12	14	9	120	3.94	I
2	IMPS-Immediate payment services	40	25	22	16	17	120	3.46	V
3	Inquiry services	45	32	25	9	9	120	3.79	II
4	Bill payment(Unit bill, Cash bill)	48	27	15	10	25	120	3.65	IV
5	Security /Safety System	35	20	25	20	20	120	3.25	VI
6	Time Savings	45	25	25	15	10	120	3.67	III

Table 3 shows that The M-Banking service is easy to Transfer Fund. So it gets 1st Rank. The Second Rank goes to Enquiry services. Also, the Time savings was ranked Third(mean score of 3.67) as one of the satisfaction factors of M-Banking. Other factors are followed by Bill payment, IMPS-Immediate payment services and security/Safety system.

Findings

- The Study found that 69% of respondents are male and the remaining 31% are female.
- The study found that 38% of respondents are under the age group of below 40 years, 50% of respondents are in the age group of 40 to 60 years and only 12% of the respondents belong to the age group of Above 60 years.
- By applying the Likert scale method, it is found that most of the respondents give the first rank to the fund transfer provided by M-Banking. The second one is Enquiry services facility followed by the Time savings, Bill payment and IMPS-Immediate payment services. The last rank is given to Security/ safety system by the respondents.

Suggestions

- The banks must improve its service quality regarding communication, responsiveness, reliability and understanding.
- To provide various effective modes for promotional schemes interaction with the customer, more accuracy in billing, financial security and privacy in transactions.
- If the banks want to increase the service quality it should enhance level of services in punctuality, transparency and accountability, quality of customers service, safety and confidentiality of transaction, No. of queues in bank branches, 24 hours services to the customers, individualized attention to customers, necessary information to customers, learn the specific requirement of customers.
- Set standards for on-boarding mobile banking customers

Conclusions

The role of technology is increasing day by day. The various sectors of India are growing much faster rate with the help of technology. Mobile banking is also a big mobile telecommunication platform of new technology, which promotes the banking functions in India. Mobile banking also helps the banks to increase their customers. Today, everyone has a mobile phone in his hands. The number of mobile users in India got the second position in the world. The increasing frequency of mobile internet users gives the boost energy to the mobile banking. This paper explores the importance of mobile banking in the new era of technology which helps the banking industry to grow at a higher speed.

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